

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Biostimulants increased soil bacterial diversity, functional diversity and the abundance of fungal symbiotrophs, and decreased fungal pathogens in horticultural Mediterranean fields

During three years, we rotated in SE Spain (semiarid Mediterranean climate) the following crops: 1. Potato, from 22/12/2020 to 04/06/2021; 2. Broccoli, from 5/10/2021 to 10/01/2022; 3. Melon, from 29/03/2022 to 14/07/2022; and 4. Potato, from 16/12/2022 to 15/05/2023. The crops were established under drip irrigation and mineral fertilization. Four fertilization treatments were designed, where we reduced mineral fertilizer to partially replace it by biostimulants: i) Inorganic fertilizers applied at the nutritional demands of the crop (F100); ii) The 50% of the rate of inorganic fertilizers added in F100 (F50); iii) F50 + the application of a formulation of nitrogen-fixing and phosphorus and potassium solubilizing bacteria (BA); and iv) F50 + the application of a formulation of bacteria and non-mycorrhizal fungi (BA+FU). The application of biostimulants enhanced N fixation, ammonification,

denitrification, and CO₂ fixation, compared to full inorganic fertilization. There was an increase in bacterial diversity with the addition of biostimulants, with changes in taxonomic composition. However, the use of biostimulants did not affect overall fungal diversity and composition. There was a decrease in the abundance of fungal pathogens and an increase in the relative abundance of fungal symbiotrophs in BAI+FU. Thus, biofertilizers increased soil bacterial diversity and changed bacterial composition, with increased soil functioning, and increases in fungal symbiotrophs abundance. The use of biostimulants can be fostered in Mediterranean horticulture to reduce the dependency on mineral fertilizers, with stimulation of beneficial microorganisms that contributes to keep high crop yields and reduce soil pathogens abundance.

1. Melon crop under drip irrigation in SE Spain

KEYWORDS

Vegetables, rotations, biostimulants, soil, biodiversity, pathogens

AUTHORSHIP

Ollio, I., Fernández J.A., Sánchez-Navarro V., Lloret E., Egea-Gilabert, C., Martínez-Martínez, S., Zornoza, R.

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